

Progress Report: Diagnostics of Health Disorders and Bio Monitoring in Aircraft Crew Members after “Fume Events”— Preliminary Results After Analyzing Patient Files

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ABBREVIATIONS

AchE	Acetylcholinesterase
FE	Fume event
HBM	Human biomonitoring
NTE	Neuropathy target esterase
OP	Organophosphates
OPIDN	Organophosphate induced delayed neuropathy
TCP	Tricresyl phosphate
VOC	Volatile organic compounds

ABSTRACT

From 2014 to 2017 patients suffering from complex symptoms after fume events attended our University clinic. The patients' files contain the clinical results from external clinics, from various UMG's departments (occupational medicine, neuropathology, neurological clinic, eye clinic) as well as the results of human biomonitoring (HBM) which were applied, taking individual complaints into account. We underline the health impairment in the context of cabin air fume events and the necessity for further independent studies for analytical and clinical pathways. Evaluation of the clinical symptoms, the causing substances and the relevant contextual factors are required.

INTRODUCTION

Crew members and passengers complain regularly about health disorders after flights. In a current report, the German Federal Bureau of Aircraft Accident Investigation

defines fume events as “any incident associated with smells, smoke or mist inside an airplane as well as impairments to the health of occupants”.¹ Regarding the scientific knowledge this topic is not new. Cabin air incidents or so-called “fume events” (FE) have been associated with various symptoms among affected persons and were already mentioned in the 1950s.

In the following period similar reports underlined repeatedly that the symptoms correlated with an FE, but neither the results collected, nor systematical investigations made over many years, nor the source of the possible contamination with unknown substances during flight, nor the measurements of clinical symptoms have been effective to provoke prevention strategies.

From 2014 to 2017 patients suffering from complex symptoms after fume events attended the University for Medicine of Göttingen's (UMG), occupational clinic'. The patients' files also contain the clinical results from external clinicians (especially of the Institute for Occupation & Maritime Medicine, Translational Toxicology & Immunology Unit of the University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Occupational Medicine Charité, Berlin, Pneumologie am Elisenhof, München, Institute for Occupational, Social and Environmental Medicine of the Friedrich Alexander University (FAU) Erlangen-Nürnberg) as well as from various of UMG's departments (occupational medicine, neuropathology, neurological clinic, eye clinic) which were applied, taking individual complaints into account. Furthermore, the results of clinical function tests and the screening for harmful substances (human biomonitoring) were documented in the patients' files.

Human biomonitoring

Human biomonitoring (HBM) is the investigation of biological material from employees for the determination of hazardous substances, their metabolites, or their biochemical or biological effect parameters. The aim of HBM is to record the exposure and health hazards of workers, to compare the analytical values obtained with appropriate assessment values and to propose appropriate measures to reduce exposure and health

hazards. The findings from HBM can be an important source of information for risk assessment and for the assessment of the effectiveness of existing occupational health and safety measures. German regulations (“Arbeitsmedizinische Regel 6.2 Biomonitoring”) state: “*Biomonitoring is useful even after accidental exposures, especially if no results from air measurements are available. Attention should be paid to a situation-appropriate assessment; the assessment results aimed at chronic effects cannot be used directly*”.

In dependence of a diagnostic time slot—the time slot after a Fume Event (FE)—blood and/or urine samples were screened for internal exposure to organophosphates (OP) and/or various volatile organic compounds (VOC).

OPs are described as a likely cause of symptoms after a fume event. Substances which inhibit the acetylcholinesterase (ACHE) or the neuropathy target esterase (NTE) are, e.g., OPs which are used among other substances as flame retardants.

Schindler *et al.* described an occupational exposure of aircrews to tricresyl phosphate (TCP) isomers and organophosphate flame retardants after fume events.² Liyasova *et al.* and Solbu *et al.* described exposure to tri-*o*-cresyl phosphate in jet airplane passengers.^{3,4} Abou-Donia *et al.* detected autoantibodies to nervous system-specific proteins in sera of flight crew members: biomarkers for the nervous system.⁵ Well-described syndromes of OP toxicity are cholinergic neurotoxicity and—for some, but not all members of this group of chemicals—the organophosphorus ester-induced delayed neuropathy.⁶

Organophosphate induced delayed neuropathy (OPIDN) involves the distal degeneration of axons of the peripheral and central nervous systems developing one to four weeks after single or short-term exposures. Characteristic signs include cramping muscle pain in the lower limbs, distal numbness and paresthesia. Known sequelae include progressive weakness and depression of deep tendon reflexes in the lower and, in severe cases,

upper limbs.^{5,7}

To be used as a biochemical effect marker in human biomonitoring studies it is important that the AChE activity in the erythrocytes of a patients’ blood sample correlates with the activity in the neurons, the target tissue of toxicity. Moreover, after reaction to organophosphates, the esteratic activity is mainly recovered after new synthesis within a period of, probably, several weeks.

Likewise, the NTE activity in the nervous tissue is correlated with the one in lymphocytes isolated from a human blood sample. Lymphocytic NTE has a regeneration half-life of probably five to seven days, enabling a sample collection after potential exposure. For the evaluation of data sets involving both enzyme activities of a single patient, it is noteworthy that there is no connection between AChE inhibition and NTE inhibition.⁶

METHODS

In the patients’ files, HBM results analyzing the erythrocytic AChE activities using the ChE check mobile® kit are described. Preliminary results described patients’ AChE activities as normal.⁸

In the patients’ files, HBM results concerning the NTE activity described preliminary low levels.⁸

So far, along with the HBM for OPs, HBM for volatile organic compounds (VOC) are described in the patients’ files. Internal exposure patterns to components (aliphatics, aromatics, ketones, alcohols) are described immediately after an FE. Special attention is given to the control values after non-exposure periods: the individual VOC concentrations after an FE showed a hundredfold increase compared to those after a flightfree period, especially concerning substances such as e.g. octane or hexane. Most of the detectable substances are not components of the general environment but are described as components of, e.g., kerosene, jet engine oil or hydraulic fluid, and are not comparable to everyday

Figure 1 – Protocol of diagnostic tools based on the panel of standardized symptoms-related diagnostic methods, with noticeable findings in patients reporting symptoms after fume events (FE).

products in the general environment. In contrast to air monitoring HBM reflects the individual load of hazards from VOCs or OP levels in symptomatic patients after a fume event (FE).

Symptom and function tests

Concerning the symptoms documented in the patients' files, various complaints were found comparable with those described in detail from other working groups, in detail respiratory problems, peripheral nervous

symptoms as well as central nervous problems such as memory problems and other cognitive complaints.

Pulmonary symptoms

The preliminary results of lung function measurements documented in the patients' files – performed in accordance to international standard (ERS/ATS standards for single-breath carbon monoxide uptake in the lung) – showed a percentage distribution of the FEV1 and VC comparable to the healthy norm population.

We can conclude that the breathing mechanism seems to be mostly undisturbed, however, the patients are symptomatic.

Therefore, we take a look at further lung function parameters concerning the oxygen intake: in symptomatic patients after an FE a shift of the distribution, compared to those of the healthy norm population, could be observed: most values were found notably under the mean value, in most of the cases the reduction shows several standard deviations compared to those of the healthy norm population. Statistical validation of the diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide (DLCO), 5% of the general population were defined as expected “not healthy”, this corresponds to Z-Score -1,645: regarding the symptomatic patients after an FE, more than 50% showed values under this point. Comparing results from different clinics it should be noted that the inter- or intra-laboratory accuracy is described as diverse due to different device types for measuring DLCO.⁹ Additionally, a measurement of the nitric oxide uptake in the lung, a relative reduction of the microvascular (VC) components compared to the membrane (DM) component can be observed. Further studies are needed to define the relative response between diffusing capacity of the lung for nitric oxide (DLNO) and DLCO under a range of perturbations such as exercise and high-altitude exposure as given during flight for crew members; these comparisons could yield mechanistic insight into alveolar microvascular recruitment.¹⁰ The results are proven by performing a bicycle-based exercise stress test detecting respiratory gases under stress. However, the irregularity of these parameters corresponds to the patients’ complaints of breathlessness under stress.

Cognitive impairment

Another symptom complex includes cognitive impairment, in particular difficulties of speaking and finding of words, memory performance, concentration problems and/or incoordination. The interim analytical findings show that about 80% of the patients struggle with symptoms of cognitive impairment and confirm one or more symptoms in most cases, specifically cognitive

impairment. This is in accordance with the results which are described from other working groups.

Peripheral nerve impairment

The patents’ files contain the evaluation of diagnostics or peripheral nervous complaints (restless legs, muscular jerking, tingling sensations), in particular, peripheral nerve function measurement and neuropathological investigation. The results of the neurography were frequently unremarkable despite credible similar patterns of complaints amongst patients. Performing standardized neuropathological diagnostics to look for a special kind of neuropathy,¹¹ so-called small fiber neuropathy which is characterized by a reduced density of epidermal nerve fibers. Our preliminary results: in nearly all patients the intra-epidermal nerve fiber showed significantly decreased densities and as such clearly under the mean value of the healthy norm population. Normally this kind of neuropathy can be detected as a long-term effect in patients with diabetes, alcoholism or after some infection such as borreliosis.

CONCLUSIONS

However, despite all of these clear findings of functional disorders, there are still many questions open concerning the diagnostic pathways of other symptoms such as cardiovascular symptoms, especially due to the findings of post-mortem reports (e.g. myocarditis), gastrointestinal symptoms, visual organ, and others.

The symptoms in patients exposed to fume events show similar patterns including various organ systems, in particular, the central and peripheral nervous system, the lung, the visual organ, the gastrointestinal tract. These symptoms can be confirmed using standardized diagnostic tests especially neurocognitive tests, monitoring the oxygen intake and neuro-histological tests. The clinical findings are conclusive in the context of the descriptions of the toxicological potential of the detected VOCs and organophosphates, for instance concerning OPIDN. Figure 1 outlines the Protocol of diagnostic tools based on the panel of standardized symptoms-related diagnostic methods with noticeable

findings in patients reporting symptoms after fume events (FE).

HBM is regarded as the method of choice in accordance with the German regulations (e.g. the “Arbeitsmedizinische Regel 6.2 Biomonitoring”) taking into account different substances which are described as components of kerosene, hydraulic fluid and/or oil, in particular OP or VOCs.

Special attention was given to the internal exposure pattern: most of the detectable substances are not components from within the general environment, but as mentioned above, components of e.g. kerosene, jet engine oil or hydraulic fluids.

Summarizing our experience regarding the patients’ files, we underline the health impairment in the context of cabin air fume events and the necessity for further independent studies for analytical and clinical pathways. Evaluation of the clinical symptoms, the causing substances and the relevant contextual factors is required. More evidence for appropriating diagnostic algorithm, appropriating therapeutic algorithm and appropriating evidence-based systematic risk assessment for good workplace safety and effective preventive measures is needed. In the long run, the aim has to be the completion of an optimal patient care strategy for therapy and rehabilitation, and prevention strategies. With reference to the last mentioned points, there is to date no evidence-based knowledge, even though fume events have been described for several decades.

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